

“SOCIAL MEDIA AND ITS PERCEIVED EFFECTS TO STUDENTS ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE”

CHAPTER I

THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

Introduction

In the century which is called the Digital age, computer and internet have gained an absolutely central importance in human life, and social media had a prominent role in this picture.

Since internet today is the most important source of information and the growing dimensions of the use of social media by students cannot be underestimated. This is because majority of the students devoted more attention and time to social media than they do for their studies and they cannot pass their examinations well if they do not learn.

Students' academic life has moved to a different dimension since the introduction of these social media networks and several studies have affirmed that social media plays an important role on students in higher education. Moreover, Adam Mahamat (2014) in his research found that the majority of respondents agreed that social networking sites have a positive impact on their academic performance.

In connection, as an educational tool, social media enriches learning by giving both students and teachers the opportunity to connect in new and very exciting ways thereby encouraging flexible mode of learning. Wherein flexible learning expands the choice on what, when and how people learn. It supports different styles of

learning including E-learning which is highly patronized across the globe. Social media undoubtedly generate new opportunities to engage students in education as they are remarkably effective at connecting people and facilitating the exchange of information. It is clear and indisputable from these studies that social media usage in the educational sector cannot be underestimated since its introduction.

However, even though social media is really beneficial to the academic performances, there are still negative effects of using social media and some are as follows; most of the students use the social media sites to chat than for academic purpose and they can no longer stop the flow of information and knowledge because now the new world of social networking allows free sharing of thoughts through online social networking sites such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and the like.

Furthermore, the study conducted by Maya (2015), revealed that media use contribute to lower academic performance, low self-perceptions and less interest in college oriented carriers. Academic excellence plays an important role in an individual's life; be it in the family, at social gatherings, at workplace, in an institution or even among peers. Much emphasis is placed on academic excellence because of the role it plays in an individual's life as far as a successful life and respect is concerned in every part of the world. Due to this, many people are concerned with the ways that they can improve their academic performance.

Today students at all levels have been engaged in the use of social networking sites. This research therefore seeks to investigate the extent social media is used by students of Farwestern University into social networking sites and also determine the effect of their use on their academic performance. The researchers generally hope to provide significant insights that lead to the improvement of students' academic performance.

Conceptual Framework

Social media is a rising trend in the world today. Communication skills are exemplified by the use of social media networking. Social media networking allows for a communication outlet. Social media is being utilized by students, parents, businesses, and religious organizations. It is being used in many forms by many different platforms for many reasons.

At present, whether social media is favorable or unfavorable, many students utilize these sites on a daily basis. As social media sites continue to grow in popularity it is our belief that technology is a vital part of today's students' success equation (Wang, Chen & Liang, 2011). Many researchers have been looking into a considerable amount of research on how social media influences student academic performances at colleges. Many parents are worried that their children are spending too much time on Facebook and other social media sites and not enough time studying.

The effects of these social media can be considered positive but also has some negative consequences. It increases student collaboration, improves participation, content rich resources and they are useful for team projects. These sites have also caused some potential harm to society. The students become victims of social networks more often than anyone else. This is because when they are studying or searching their course material online, they get attracted to these sites to kill the boredom in their study time, diverting their attention from their work and they are more likely to drink and use drug.

Figure 01: Paradigm of the Study

The researchers develop paradigm of the study (Figure 1) showing an input to what extent respondents use social media in terms of membership to social network, no. of times account is visited in a day, number of years that respondents have been using social media, hours spent by respondents on social media activities and uses for social media. Likewise, it presents the perceptions of students towards the effects of social media to academic performance. The process involves the use of descriptive survey design which used questionnaire as an instrument. Descriptive statistics like

frequency, percentage and weighted were the basic tools for analysis. As an output, the research established a responsible use of social media as a means of learning.

Statement of the Problem

This study generally aimed to determine the perceived effects of social media in the academic performance of students at Farwestern University for the school year 2018-2019.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. To what extent social media is used by the respondents relative to:
 - a. membership to social network
 - b. no. of times account is visited in a day
 - c. length of time that respondents have been using social media
 - d. hours spent by respondents on social media activities
 - e. uses for social media
2. What are the effects of social media to academic performance as perceived by the respondents?

Scope and Limitations

This study focused on the effects of social media to the academic performance of the students at Farwestern University. One hundred twelve (112) students were selected as respondents of the study and were chosen through representative sampling.

Descriptive survey design was used since it explored to what extent the social media was used by the respondents in terms of their membership to social network, number of times their accounts were visited in a day, length of time they have been using social media, hours spent on social media activities and uses for social media.

Also, it explored the perceived effects of social media to the academic performance of the students.

In gathering the data, it made use of survey questionnaire adapted from Popoola B. (2017) posted in www.surveymonkey.com/r/pcbgr. Reliability, validity of the instrument and the results of the research were considered limitations to be subjected to further validation.

Significance of the Study

Social media is website and application that enable user to create and share content or to participate in social media activities. This study can generally be the basis in the academe in relation to using social media as a means of learning.

Specifically, this would be useful to number of people especially in the academe.

Teachers can be guided in incorporating social media in pedagogy highlighting limitations and control.

Parents become aware of the advantages and disadvantages of social media in their children's academic studies.

Also, the **researchers** were able to enhance their research skills and served as a motivation to conduct more studies.

Finally the **future researchers** can make use of the results as an input to their respective further studies.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

This part presents relevant foreign and local literature that has significant bearing with the present study. These significant information and discussions greatly helped the researcher to gain deeper understanding of this study that focuses on the social media and academic performance of the students of Farwestern University.

RELATED LITERATURE

This portion presents related literature, which comprise both foreign and local literature and studies. The insights culled from these readings proved valuable in the development and completion of the study.

FOREIGN LITERATURE

According to Austin (2016), social media is an integral part of today's society. With loads of information being disseminated over the Internet, social media has become the very fabric upon which our society is being built. The people who are at the forefront of molding the future of social networking sites are teens and children. This is because vast majorities of the people who use the Internet are children and teens.

Ana Maria De La Cruz (2017) stated in her Blog the Positive and Negative use of Social Media by Students wherein Social media are online technology platforms that help to connect people together far and near. It is used to build relationship among people. The use of social media by students helps to have access to basic information as quick as possible. Moreover, the use of online platforms such as school website will give students the right access to quality information about the school environment, departments, faculties, rules, and regulations. It has been observed that social media has

a wider and faster means of circulating information not only to the students of an institution but also to the generality of the public. Where Social media platforms available to students includes Facebook, WhatsApp, Google Plus, Blogs, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube and much more

Abhishek Karadkar (2015) stated in his Article, that social media illuminates the lives of thousands of people by spreading knowledge internationally, thereby making us global citizens. Further, Dublin (2015) said that Social media is a fundamental part of daily life for most people. Where schools are no exception because many schools have started tapping social media to provide better service and assistance to teachers and students.

More over Al-Tarawneh (2014), believe that Facebook can be a great tool for the following tasks, which contributes to a better performance: Communication, socialization, coordination, collaboration and entertainment. However, Performancing Blog (2012) discussed the negative effects of social networking sites which outweigh the positive ones. These sites have caused some potential harm to society. The students become victims of social networks more often than anyone else. This is because of the reason that when they are studying or searching their course material online, they get attracted to these sites to kill the boredom in their study time, diverting their attention from their work.

FOREIGN STUDIES

Nee, Chee Ken (2014) investigated the impacts of incorporating Edmodo (e-learning) as educational network, into a classroom setting on the academic achievement of Biology students based on three types of conceptual level comprises of direct, simple, and complex concept. The results indicated that students that were instructed by the instruction with intervention performed a larger on the gain scores of all the three cognitive levels; than those instructed by the conventional approaches. This educational network will permeate all facets of the curriculum as a new paradigm of teaching tools

In addition, researchers like Choney (2010), San Miguel (2009) and Enriquez (2010) shows that students' use of the social media sites and level of academic performance are inversely related. Nielsen Media Research study conducted in June 2010 stated that almost one-fourth of the students spend their valuable time on the internet, in general, and on social networking sites in particular (Wade C. Jacobsen, B.S., and Renata Forste, 2011). The American Educational Research Association conducted a research and clearly mentioned that social media users study less and generate lower grade (Calimlim, M. E, 2014). Further, friendship networks oftentimes demand access to information and knowledge directly and indirectly, and impressions of friendly relationship webs on student academic performance are already affirmed (Baldwin, 2016). A student's adherence in actions such as making acquaintances on Social Networking Sites need to be seen as students bearing access to crucial information. This can be conveyed toward improving the students' academic performance. It has been analyzed that cyberspace use for educational activities and some pertinent task such as online tutorials, online lectures and training material

downloading are beneficial. However, using internet for only social networking is, indeed, useless and perhaps dangerous as well. Thus, the pros and cons of networking sites in reality, depends on the ability and willingness of the concerned individual, of whether they would be able to harness the opportunity, as well as have the capacity to cope with academic performances (K Banquil, C Burce, N Chua & S Dianalan, 2009).

According to Peter (2015), though Social media have negative effects on teenagers such as lack of privacy, distracting students from their academic work, taking most of their productive time, and such like, they also have benefits and can be used appropriately. For instance, students can form online communities in order to plan for a project, have group discussions about class material, or use the Social networking sites(SNS) as a way to keep in contact when a student who has been absent needs to be updated on current academic information.

According to Badri et. Al (2017), some benefits from using social media networks include sharing information and ideas and improving reading skills. Despite the benefits of participation of students in social media networks, its misuse could affect the academic life of the students and, thereby, their performance. Therefore, social media networks compete with academic work for students' attention. It is therefore the responsibility of the student to make the right decision in relation to the use of social media networks.

LOCAL LITERATURE

According to Astrodello (2016), people all over the world have been enjoying the benefits of using technology nowadays. In the past, communicating and free sharing of thought between people are restricted by long distance, race, and even

religion. But now these barriers can no longer stop the flow of information and knowledge because now the new world of social networking allows free sharing of thoughts through online social networking sites such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and the like.

Althaf Marsoof (2015) in his article entitled “Online social networking and the right to privacy: the conflicting rights of privacy and expression” gives a detailed description about how the advancement of Information Technology has hastened the ability to disseminate information across the globe. In particular, the recent trends in ‘Social Networking’ have led to a spark in personally sensitive information being published on the World Wide Web. While such socially active websites are creative tools for expressing one's personality it also entails serious privacy concerns. Thus, Social Networking websites could be termed a double edged sword. It is important for the law to keep abreast of these developments in technology. The major theme of the study was to demonstrate the limits of extending existing laws to battle privacy intrusions in the Internet especially in the context of social networking. It is suggested that privacy specific legislation is the most appropriate means of protecting online privacy. In doing so it is mandatory to maintain a balance in the competing right of expression, failure of which may hinder the benefits offered by Internet technology.

LOCAL STUDIES

Morillo (2014) perceived effects of SNSs to the students’ academic performance show that SNSs contribute in the attainment of higher grade by interacting online about school work. The results show that there is no significant relationship between SNSs usage and student academic performance because

correlation coefficients show a negative relationship between SNSs use and academic performance. The probability result has a very small average of correlation, thus the study found a negligible relationship between SNSs and academic performance.

Astodello (2016) observed in her study Impacts of social media academic lives, academic performance at the Tabuk City National High School the same positive and negative impact of using social media inside and outside the classroom. Wherein social sites are helpful in communicating with students, reminding them of their assignments and urgent requirements. In addition, social sites as referred to her students is a helpful resources that could fetch them higher grades in academics.

As a result, almost 85 percent of the students were able cope with their academic difficulties and at least 65 to 75 percent of the class obtained the average level of performance. However, Astodello, recommended that students should be encouraged to limit the time they spend on social media sites and be advised to rather substitute those hours with reading some learning materials – short stories, novels, etc. to improve their vocabulary. Since the use of social media sites had affected the academic performance of students negatively, there is a need to introduce the students other information resources or materials that would motivate and help them perform well in their academics.

Tamayo and Dela Cruz (2014) concluded in their study that that seventy one (71) or 51.4% of the respondents have reached below satisfactory grade average and only sixty seven (67) or 48.6% students have successfully reached the satisfactory academic performance. That more than 50% of the respondents performed below satisfactorily at school. Student's diversion from school activities to Social Media usage largely affect their academic performance. Based on the results of the study, using Social Media has effect on Student's Academic Performance. Students who

participated in the study rarely participate on class activities, perform well on class and attend class regularly. A moderate correlation or relationship of +0.690 is higher than the tabular value of +1.000 at .05 level of significance, therefore the null hypothesis is rejected and that there is no significant relationship between Social Media and academic Performance of the BSIT students of CEU-Malolos. That scatter diagram depicts the frequency of Social Media usage affects the academic performance of the students. Students with lower grades are Frequent User of Social Media while the Occasional User tends to concentrate on school works and get satisfactory ratings. Moreover, he recommended Teachers should be aware and orient the students on how to use Social Media moderately. Monitor school work diligently and encourage students to indulge to a more fulfilling and productive activities. Social Media can be an aid in classroom activities. Since youth are Social Media involved now a days and nothing can keep them away to that, it is better to utilized this technology to a more productive way.

SYNTHESIS

The studies cited in this chapter give a clear picture of the diversity in studies on Social Networking Sites. The Social Networking Sites are a highly important medium of communication and entertainment, especially for youth. As a matter of fact youngsters are far more attracted than any group of people to Social Networking Sites. This may be due to the vast advantages that these sites provide including better access to people around the world, instant messaging, video calling, access to various products and services of many companies and brands and much more. In this era the development of technology and its accessibility has enabled rapid expansion and popularity of Social networking Sites. Consequently this global phenomenon is affecting interpersonal relationships of many. This aspect only

stresses upon a detailed research work to be carried out involving interpersonal relationships and Social Networking Sites.

As such, the present study primarily focuses on Social media and academic performance of the students at Farwestern University students. All the studies mentioned in the review give a plethora of views about Social Networking Sites and media which correctly position the importance of the present study. It is noteworthy that not many researchers have been undertaken regarding interpersonal relationships of High school students and Social media Sites in Isabela.

CHAPTER III

Methodology and Procedure

This chapter described how this study was conducted. It presents comprehensive description of the research method used, the procedures in gathering the needed data and statistical treatments that the researcher employed.

Research Design

The researchers used descriptive survey research design where it explored to what extent the social media was used by the respondents in terms of their membership to social network, number of times their accounts were visited in a day, length of time they have been using social media, hours spent on social media activities and uses for social media. Also, it explored the perceived effects of social media to the academic performance of the students.

A descriptive survey (Faltado, R., 2016) attempts to establish the range and distribution of some social characteristics, such as education or training, occupation, and location, and to discover how these characteristics may be related to certain behavior patterns or attitudes.

Descriptive survey aims to determine or describe, or to identify what is (Ethridge, D.E., 2004) and casts light on current issues or problems through a process of data collection that enables them to describe the situation more completely than was possible without employing this method (Fox, W. & Bayat, M.S.; cited in <http://researchmethodology.net.2017>)

Research Locale

The study entitled “The Perceived Effects of Social Media to the Academic Performance of Students” was conducted at Farwestern University. It is considered a large school with a total population of 454. It offers both Junior and Senior High School wherein two tracks are offered General Academic Strand and Technology-Vocational-Livelihood. Two specializations are there in TVL which are Information and Communication Technology and Home Economics.

Samples and Sampling Procedure

In this study, the researchers used representative sampling to identify the respondents. Out of 454 total number of population, the researchers yielded 112 respondents of the study. A representative sample is a group or set chosen from a larger statistical population or group of factors or instances that adequately replicates the larger group according to whatever characteristic or quality is under study (Hall, M.,2018)

Research Instrument

In order to gather the data, the researcher designed a questionnaire adapted from the survey questionnaire of Popoola B. (2017) posted in www.surveymonkey.com/r/pcbgr. It is comprised of two parts: 6-item questions in checklist form and 9-item statements in a four-point Likert Scale ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree with numerical values of 1,2,3,& 4 respectively.

Survey research questionnaire, according to De Franzo (2012), is useful in describing the characteristics of a large population. No other research method can

provide this broad capability, which ensures a more accurate sample to gather targeted results in which to draw conclusions and make important decisions.

Data Gathering Procedure

In collecting the data, the researchers developed first the instrument to be used. After which, they seek permission from the School Head. The respondents were selected and screened through representative sampling. Consent from the participants was obtained and assured that their answers will be treated with confidentiality.

During the process of data collection, the respondents were instructed clearly. When there were no clarifications, the researchers proceeded to the distribution of the survey questionnaires to the students.

After the retrieval of such questionnaires, computation, interpretation and analysis of the data were conducted to come up with the final results for conclusion and further recommendations.

Chapter IV

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

The Extent Social Media is Used by Respondents

Table 1: Membership to Social Network

Social Media Network	Frequency (n=112)	Percentage
Facebook	95	84.82
Twitter	2	1.79
YouTube	10	8.92
Google	4	3.57
Instagram	1	0.90

As shown in the table, majority has facebook account as indicated by 95 out of 112 respondents or 84.82 percent. It is noticeable that only few have youTube account with 10 or 8.92 percent, google with 4 or 3.57 percent and instagram with 1 or 0.90 percent.

This implies that facebook has become the most popular social media platform that caters not only to the young but also to the old generation. In the global context, 47 billion people on average log onto Facebook daily and are considered daily active users(Facebook DAU) for June 2018, which represents an 11 percent increase year over year (Source: Facebook as 07/25/18).

Table 2: Number of Times Respondents Visit their Account in a Day

Times they visit their Account	Frequency	Percentage
1-2	62	55.36
2-3	25	22.32
3-5	25	22.32

The table shows that majority of the respondents are visiting their account in 1-2 times daily with the frequency of 62 or 55.36 percent. On the other hand, both 2-3 & 3-5 got a frequency of 25 or 22.32 percent.

It can be inferred that social media is an integral part of students' life. Being in this digital age, they actively engage themselves in their created accounts.

Table 3: Years Respondents Have Been Using Social Media

Years they are Using Social Media	Frequency	Percentage
1-2 years	55	49.11
3-4 years	31	27.68
5+ years	26	23.21

The table discloses that most of the respondents have been using social media platforms for two years. This is followed by length of using social media platforms for 3-4 years with 31 or 27.68 percent and 5+ years with 26 or 23.21 percent.

The result manifested that years spent using social media platforms are relatively close and considered long enough. This clearly shows that respondents enjoy and completely immersed in the world of technology.

Table 4: Hours Respondents Spend on Social Media Activities in a Day

Hours they Spend on Social Networking Activities	Frequency	Percentage
1-2 hours	57	50.89
2-3 hours	33	29.46
4-5 hours	15	13.39
5-6 hours	1	0.89
More than 6 hours	6	5.36

As shown in the table, the highest hours they spend in social media activities are 1-2 hours with the frequency of 57 or 50.89%. It is followed by 2-3 hours with the frequency of 33 or 29.46%, 4-5 hours with the frequency of 15 or 13.39%, more than 6 with the frequency of 6 or 5.36% and 5-6 hours with the frequency of 1 or 0.89%, respectively.

It can be inferred from the table that the respondents spent 1-2 hours browsing/using facebook could affect their study time. It is an interfering factor in doing their assignments or academic related activities. According to Pew Research's latest survey, 74 percent of Facebook users visit the site daily and 51 percent go several times a day.

Table 5: Respondents' Reasons in Using Social Media

Uses for Social Media	Frequency	Percentage
Social	50	45.04
Games	25	22.32
Professional	0	0
Academic	37	33.04

As shown in the table they use social media for social activities with the frequency of 50 or 45.04 percent. This is followed by academic purpose with the frequency of 37 or 33.04 percent, games with the frequency of 25 or 22.32 percent respectively. On the other hand, none uses social media for professional reasons.

It can be inferred from the result that most of the students use it for social activities. According to m.raisingchildren.net.au, teens make use of social media to have fun, make and maintain friendships, share interests, develop identities and develop relationships with family. It is their priority over using social media for academic studies.

Table 7: Social Media and Academic Performance of Students

Statement	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Category
1. Social media/network is used to communicate with teacher for academic purposes.	2.96	Agree
2. Social media allows sharing of works collaboratively with my peers.	2.89	Agree
3. Social media motivate students to participate in classroom activities.	2.65	Agree
4. Social media allows sharing of notes and information about lectures.	2.72	Agree
5. Integrating social media in the lesson boost student's interest in learning new concepts.	2.72	Agree
6. Social media/networks while doing assignments, negatively affects the quality of your work.	2.77	Agree
7. Social media leads to procrastination or delay of academic tasks.	2.92	Agree
8. Social network distract learners to do their assignments and review their lessons.	2.79	Agree
9. Social network hinders student's social life which affects their academic performance.	2.79	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	2.80	Agree

It can be gleaned from the table that the respondents generally agree that social media influence their academic performance with a weighted mean of 2.80.

As perceived by students, social media has both positive and negative effects. Perceived positive effects were using social media to communicate with teacher for academic purposes (2.96), allowing sharing of works collaboratively with peers (2.89), allowing sharing of notes and information about lectures and boosting students' interest in learning new concepts (2.72), and motivating students to participate in classroom activities respectively (2.65).

On the other hand, the perceived negative effects of social media were leading to procrastination or delay of academic tasks (2.92), distracting learners to do their assignments and review their lessons and hindering student's social life which affects their academic performance (2.79), and affecting the quality of assignment (2.65).

Teachers see the educational potential of social media; they use the platforms to continue important lessons beyond the reach of the classroom. But less carefully coordinated interactions leave both the student and teacher exposed as their personal and school-based lives intertwine in unexpected ways.

Chapter V

Summary

The researchers used descriptive survey research design where it explored to what extent the social media was used by the respondents in terms of their membership to social network, number of times their accounts were visited in a day, length of time they have been using social media, hours spent on social media activities and uses for social media. Also, it explored the perceived effects of social media to the academic performance of the students.

Respondents of the study were 112 students of Farwestern University chosen through representative sampling.

In order to gather data, the researcher designed questionnaire adapted from Popoola B. (2017).

Based on the statistical analysis conducted from the data collected in the study, it was found out that as to the extent of using social media:

- a. Majority uses facebook account as indicated by 95 out of 112 respondents or 84.82 percent.
- b. Most of the respondents are visiting their account in 1-2 times daily with the frequency of 62 or 55.36 percent.
- c. Many of the respondents have been using social media platforms for two years.
- d. The highest hours they spend in social media activities are 1-2 hours with the frequency of 57 or 50.89 percent.

- e. Common use of social media is for social activities with the frequency of 50 or 45.04 percent.

On the other hand, respondents generally perceived that social media influence their academic performance both positively and negatively with a weighted mean of 2.80.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that as to the extent of using social media, the common social media platform used by the respondents was facebook mainly for social activities. Indulging themselves in such activities both have advantages and disadvantages in their academic performance.

Recommendations

With the findings and conclusions discussed above, the following recommendations are suggested:

1. The school administration must conduct any social media-related information dissemination regarding the effects of social media to one's study. At the same time intensify regulation or control towards the use of social media platforms.
2. The teachers, as well, must also help to fill the insufficient knowledge of the students in being a responsible social media user.
3. Parents must also hands-on in guiding their child towards being a responsible user of any sites.
4. Students, as the greatly affected, must also consider every action done towards any of their social media account.

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